

K-Mer Index Of DNA Sequence Based On Hash Algorithm

Jinlin Liu¹, Qiang Chen² and Chen Zhang³

¹College of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, Shanghai University of Engineering Science, Shanghai 201620,China.

²College of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, Shanghai University of Engineering Science, Shanghai 201620,China.

³School of Management, Shanghai University of Engineering Science Shanghai, 201620, China.

ABSTRACT

K-mer frequency statistics of biological sequences is a very important and important problem in biological information processing. This paper addresses the problem of index k-mer for large scale data reading DNA sequences in a limited memory space and time. Using the hash algorithm to establish index, the index model is set up to base pairing, and get the length of k-mer statistic information quickly, so as to avoid searching all the sequences of the index. At the same time, the program uses hash table to establish index and build search model, and uses the zipper method to resolve the conflict in the case of address conflict. Algorithm of time complexity analysis and experimental results show that compared with the traditional indexing methods, the algorithm of the performance improvement is obvious, and very suitable for to be used in the k-mer length change with a wide range .

KEYWORDS

K-mer index; hash algorithm; DNA detecting; index model;

1.INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of DNA sequencing technology in recent years, human generated massive biological sequence data, and we need to analyze and process through effective calculation means. Among the numerous biological sequence analysis and processing problems, the k-mer of biological sequence data is a short sequence of DNA sequences of k sequences. When the K value is appropriate, sequence k-mer frequency distribution contains all the information in the genome constituting equivalent sequences .So we can learn biological sequences of base distribution characteristics, functions, structures and evolution information by analyzing DNA sequence k-mer distribution and different k-mer information

2.QUESTIONS

This paper aims to solve the problem of k-mer index of DNA sequence.According to the given K, 100 million DNA sequences will establish index, Then the computer will read every K length DNA from the start to end for each sequence. Then move on to the next sequence to read again, until the positions of the individual K-mer appeared in the sequence were recorded. Because

DNA sequencing fragments, large scale of data, so we have to handle large data sets under the condition of limited memory and disk space, and make the space complexity and computational complexity as much as possible has been optimized. So we have to solve these problems.

Q1.

According to the given K to establish index, then search every sequence. Each sequence uses a hash algorithm to encode the base, and then convert the input specific K base fragment into the decimal data, and then match in the 100 million sequence. In the end, the computer output line and column base fragment.

Q2.

After the index is established, we build the hash table in memory, and every time we traverse, we store the frequency and the position of the k-mer in the hash table. Under the limited memory space, we can traverse a million DNA sequences.

3.PROBLEM ANALYSIS

3.1.problem abstraction.

First according to the 100 million genetic sequence, because the length of each gene sequence is 100, so gene sequence is equivalent to a two bit matrix array a, corresponding to the rows of a as: 1-1 000000, it is listed as the 1-100. The problem is abstracted from the matrix $A[i][j]$ analysis, $i=1,2,\dots, 1000000$; $j=1,2,\dots, 100$.

3.2.Method solution

The base species of the sequence are: C, A, G, T. Using the hash algorithm, the four bases are converted into four binary digits, and then the conversion sequence is converted, which is set $A=0, C=1, G=2, T=3$, and then convert the four numbers to decimal digits in the matching query. Hash value algorithm formula is $\text{Hash}(\text{value})=\text{value}*[4^{(k-m-1)}]$, value represents the corresponding value of the character, K represents the length of M, and k-mer represents the position range of the character in the string $[0-(m-1)]$. For example, the sequence $k=4$ of a given ATCG is converted into the corresponding decimal $\text{ATCG}=[0*(4^3)+3*(4^2)+2*(4^1)+1*(4^0)]=54$. The base sequence of each row length of 100 can be converted to a $100-k+1$ decimal number. The same principle can be used for the same 1 million line base sequence, you can get the corresponding decimal number and then stored in the two-dimensional array $A[i][j]$. when the same decimal number is matched, the program converts decimal conversion into a four - band form of a corresponding length of K, like the example ATCG form. Then program will print base fragment corresponding row and column labels mark.

After the establishment of the index, we use division method to build hash tables in memory, and determine the address of the hash table. The column headers and corresponding location is stored in the hash table every k-mer occurs. The search efficiency of the query million DNA sequences is improved under the limited memory space.

4.MODEL ESTABLISHMENT AND SOLUTION

Hash algorithm is the binary value of arbitrary length is mapped into a shorter fixed length of the binary value, this small binary value called hash value.

In this paper, according to the principle of hash algorithm, the identity of the four bases of the ACGT respectively 0123, converted to four hexadecimal number is then transformed into a decimal number, let base conversion of decimal number and the first line of 100-k+1 to a decimal number to match, if the base sequence matching, the program will output the row and column label mark.

Flow chart as shown below:

4.1. Model two: search model based on hash table

The main requirement of this paper is to design hash function, according to the keyword k-mer to build hash table.

There are a lot of methods of constructing hash function, digital analysis method, the direct method of definite value, random numbers, random number method is usually used in the key word length, this paper selects division method. The obtained nucleotide sequence of hash values divided by 1000 to take over, get the number as the address of the hash table. All to take over the business of the same number into the bucket, and in each bucket will remainder exists is not the same, but business the same. Therefore, in order to solve the address conflict.

The method of the zipper is to resolve the conflict: the nodes of all keywords are synonymous with the same single linked list.. If the selected hash table length is m , the hash table can be defined as an array of pointers consisting of a m pointer $T[0..M-1]$. All the hash address for the node of I , are inserted into the single $T[i]$ pointer to the single chain table. The initial values of each component in T should be null pointer. In the zipper method, the load factor can be greater than 1, but generally take α less than 1.

Hash search: first of all, k-mer as the keyword, and program needs to use the hash function to calculate the address. If the base arrangement is the same as the base sequence of the searched sequence, if the same output of the node is all the information, if the relative should be found, then returns continue to search.

4.2.Model three: analysis of the memory space occupied by the hash table

Data definition analysis: int keyword denotes an integer, whose range from negative - 2147483647 to +2147483647 (including these two digits) (32 bits) of integer. The number of bytes occupied per int type is 4B. The char holds no symbol for the 16 bit (double byte) code bits, whose values range from 0 to 65535 (8 bits).

The number of bytes occupied per char type is 1B.

Overall data analysis:

row, 1000000 defined int type variable (4Byte)

Column, 100 defined char type variable (1Byte)

Each index information theory takes up the memory space size: (B), can also be converted into memory occupancy size: (GB)

$$\left(\frac{5 \times 4^k}{1024 \times 1024 \times 1024} \right)$$

Different K values, the memory space corresponding to each index is shown in the table below

Table4.1 The Memory Space

K	Memory Space (GB)
1	0.00000002
2	0.00000007
3	0.00000030
4	0.00000119
5	0.00000477
6	0.00001907
7	0.00007629

8	0.00030518
9	0.00122070
10	0.00488281
11	0.01953125
12	0.07812500
13	0.31250000
14	1.25000000
15	5.00000000
16	20.00000000

5.RUN RESULTS SHOW

5.1.The interface

Figure5.1 The interface

5.2. Search interface

Figure5.2 the search interface

5.3. File generated results

K_mer.txt file shown in Figure

Figure5.3 the text file shown

5.4.Results the output interface

Figure5.4 the output interface

5.5.The complexity of the algorithm

(1) establish index complexity analysis

Time complexity $O(1) + O(m)$, m for the conflict when the length of the zipper, that is deep.

Space complexity $O()$

(2) using index complexity analysis

Time complexity $O(1)$

Space complexity $O(1)$

6.CONCLUSIONS

In order to solve the problem of k-mer index DNA, three kinds of models are proposed, the hash algorithm index model, the hash table query model, and the memory analysis model of hash table. The design uses the visual2010 software to traverse the optimal results, and the occupancy memory is small, the traversal efficiency is high and the result is accurate. To provide a good solution for solving the problem of k-mer index DNA.

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Authors

Jinlin Liu is currently studying in Mechanical and Electronic Engineering from Shanghai University of Engineering Science, China, where he is working towards the Master degree. His current research interests include FPGA, design and develop in Embedded system.

